

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR

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Annotation. This article examines the socio-psychological characteristics of adolescents with destructive behavior, the specifics of aggressive behavior in adolescence, as well as a system of actions that lead destructive behavior in violation of accepted norms in society and manifest themselves in the form of unbalanced mental processes, maladaptation, violations of the process of self-realization or deviations in moral or aesthetic terms. We are talking about the study of factors influencing the destructive behavior of adolescents and young people.

Key words. deviant behavior, cultural context, adolescents, traditional and transitive society, socio-cultural aspect, anxiety, emotional stupidity, psychotherapy.

Introduction. Deviant adolescents are characterized by such features of the emotional-volitional sphere as increased anxiety, defectiveness of the value system, especially in the field of goals and the meaning of life. They are, as a rule, impulsive, irritable, quick-tempered, aggressive, conflicted, which makes it difficult for such teenagers to communicate with others and creates significant difficulties in their upbringing.

For a full-fledged existence, a teenager needs constant resistance (environmental factors, internal conditions) to his aspirations to satisfy his own needs, since such resistance provides the phenomenon of actual well-being and creates opportunities for development. On the other hand, overcoming resistance to satisfying a particular need always causes tension, which, in the absence of an appropriate emotional and volitional resource, leads to destructive effects: conflicts, stress, aggression, deviations.

Adolescent deviations are characterized by high personal involvement, understated criticism of the committed offense and the possibility of relapse. At the same time, the offense is often assessed by the teenager himself as an expression of independence and a manifestation of some kind of "heroism". Most often, minors commit offenses against peers or other persons, which are characterized as a violation of the rights and security of the individual, that is, adolescents use aggression against these persons.

Teenagers with antisocial aggression differ significantly from their more socially successful peers. They express their aggression more often and more directly. Aggressive teenagers who violate the laws do not trust others, avoid situations in which they may find themselves emotionally dependent. They are less friendly to their peers, often mix sex and aggression, practically feel no guilt for aggressive behavior, obey external rather than internal restrictions. Such teenagers act almost to their own detriment, since as a result of their actions they lose their attachments and fall under the strict control of government representatives, to whom they have neither trust nor respect.

Aggressive behavior of adolescents is divided by specialists into two groups:

1. Unsocialized forms of aggressive behavior that are not hostile in nature and do not aim to cause harm to another person.
2. Socialized forms of aggressive behavior characterized by hostility and aimed at causing harm or pain to another person.

The motives of one's own behavior may be realized by a teenager, but more often the commission of aggressive actions is prompted and supported by unconscious tendencies. The psychological purpose of aggression can be both to cause suffering and harm to the victim, and to achieve other results. The most common targets of aggressive behavior may be:

- revenge for the suffering suffered;
- causing damage;
- domination, power over another person;
- receiving material benefits;
- affective discharge, resolution of intrapersonal conflict;
- self-affirmation, self-esteem enhancement, self-esteem preservation;
- protection from real or imagined threat and suffering;
- upholding personal autonomy and freedom;
- gaining authority in a peer group;
- removing obstacles to meeting needs;
- attracting attention.

A specific feature of aggressive behavior in adolescence is the dependence of a teenager on a group of peers against the background of the collapse of the authority of adults. At this age, the ability to be aggressive friends is often perceived as the presence of strength. Any teenage group has its own rituals and myths supported by the leader. For example, initiation rituals for group members or novice trials are widespread. Rituals strengthen the sense of belonging to the group and give teenagers a sense of security, and myths become the ideological basis of its life. The latter are widely used by the group to justify its intra-group and external aggression. Violence, "spiritualized" by the group myth, is experienced by teenagers as a statement of their strength, as heroism and devotion to the group.

In some cases, the initiators of aggressive behavior may be individual outsider teenagers, maladapted for various reasons and attempting to assert themselves through aggression. The manifestation of aggressiveness is determined by the status of the teenager in the group. The highest level of aggression is observed among leaders and "outcasts". Leaders strengthen their primacy through aggressive actions, and those rejected by the group through aggression show dissatisfaction with their position.

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